

Simulation approaches for delamination propagation in composite panels subjected to out-of-plane bending

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Aim of the project

- Benchmark of simulations of delamination propagation modelling techniques

Non-
standard
tests

Circular
delamination
front

Out-of-plane
loading

Case study

How to model delamination?

LEFM

- ✓ Strain Energy Release Rate (SERR)
- ✓ Fracture toughness G_c

Delamination starts:
 $SERR > G_c$

COHESIVE MODELLING

- ✓ Damage status
- ✓ Traction-separation law
Describes how the two surfaces in contact detach from each other
- ✓ Simulation of the debonding of the structure

Experimental setup

To validate the results obtained from the simulations, this study replicates an experimental test on carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) panels under quasi-static out-of-plane bending^[1].

Experimental setup

➤ Quasi-static out-of-plane bending test

➤ M30SC-150-DT120-34F

➤ $[(0/90/45/-45)_s // (90/0/45/-45)_s]$

➤ Fully clamped panels

➤ Experimental results

■ Teflon insert

■ Delamination in middle interface between two panels

■ Delamination migrated in the upper ply

Modelling – Design and BCs

PANEL DESIGN

- ✓ 140x140 mm
- ✓ 2,5 mm thickness
- ✓ Partitions to tailor mesh
- ✓ Encastre in the purple region

Modelling - Design

Modelling - Design

Modelling - Material

MATERIAL

✓ M30SC-150-DT120-34F

✓ Stacking sequence
[[0/90/45/-45]_s/(90/0/45/-45)_s]

✓ Mechanical properties

E_1	145 GPa	G_{12}	3.8 GPa
E_2	6.4 GPa	G_{13}	3.8 GPa
E_3	6.4 GPa	G_{23}	2.232 GPa

✓ Fracture toughness

G_{IC} [kJ/m ²]	G_{IIC} [kJ/m ²]	G_{IIIC} [kJ/m ²]
0.611	1.02	1.02

Modelling - Mesh

Modelling - Mesh

MESH CHARACTERISTICS

- ✓ Continuum shell elements
- ✓ Global seed: 1 mm
- ✓ Local seed: one-element thickness
- ✓ Pre-crack

Delamination modelling

Two main approaches for delamination propagation modelling: VCCT and CZM.

VCCT

- ✓ Computation of SERR
- ✗ Mesh dependence

COHESIVE CONTACT

- ✓ Less mesh dependence
- ✗ No SERR computation

Simulation variations

2

Application of VCCT with real fracture toughness values

G_I [kJ/m^2]	G_{II} [kJ/m^2]	G_{III} [kJ/m^2]
0.611	1.02	1.02

LAYUP

0°
90°
45°
-45°

Simulation variations

3

Application of cohesive contact in the middle interface

LAYUP

Simulation variations

4

Application of a combination of VCCT and cohesive contact

Load application: Spring

➤ Experimental

➤ Numerical

Load application: Spring

PROBLEM

**STIFFNESS VALUE that MATCHES the
LOAD-DISPLACEMENT CURVE does NOT
MATCH the ACTUAL DISPLACEMENT**

**Problem in the
numerical model**

**Problem in the
experimental model**

Load application: Spring

**Problem in the
experimental model**

SPRING-DEFINED MODELS

STANDARD LOAD APPLICATION

No spring introduction

**STIFFNESS matching LOAD-
DISPLACEMENT curve**

**STIFFNESS matching ACTUAL
DISPLACEMENT**

Results: No propagation simulations

Strain Energy Release Rate

✗ $K=500$ N/mm G_{II} does not reach GC threshold → **NO propagation**

MESH DEPENDENCE

✗ G_{II} symmetric at 180°, NOT at 90°

✗ G_I and G_{III} presence

Results: Propagation simulations

- ✓ Propagation shape: 45°
- ✗ Propagation orientation \neq experimental

MESH DEPENDENCE

- ✗ More mesh-dependent due to mesh discontinuities since propagation is permitted

Results: Cohesive contact simulations

■ Bonded nodes ■ Debonded nodes

FINER MESH

MESH DEPENDENCE

LESS mesh dependent

Results do NOT vary with mesh density or quality

Results: Cohesive contact simulations

■ Bonded nodes ■ Debonded nodes

Curvature plotting from DIC analysis

✓ Propagation shape

✗ Propagation orientation: 90°

MESH DEPENDENCE

✓ **LESS** mesh dependent

Results: Double-approach simulations

UPPER PLY

- ✓ Cohesive contact captures delamination **MIGRATION**

- ✓ **DELAMINATION MIGRATION** was reproduced

Damage status
STD loading
simulation

Damage status
K=6000 N/mm
simulation

- Delamination migration is faster
- Relaxation of VCCT

- Migration interface is weaker
- As enough energy is stored delamination migrates

Results: Double cohesive contact simulation

- a) Experimental results
- b) Damage status in **mid interface**
- c) Damage status in **upper ply**

✓ Cohesive contact captures both delamination in **mid interface** and migration in **upper ply**

- ✓ Propagation shape
- ✗ Propagation orientation: 90°

Conclusions

Good performance of VCCT, but high mesh dependence

Cohesive contact:

- Good performance
- No mesh dependence

Double cohesive contact approach:

- Good performance on both interfaces
- Reproduction of delamination migration in the upper ply, as in the experiment

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